

12th International Manikin and Modelling Meeting
29-31 August 2018, St. Gallen, Switzerland

Confrontation of thermal sensation and comfort models to votes in a transient thermal exposure

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1404546

Ilango Thiagalingam¹, Sidali Mokdad¹, Roch El Khoury^{1*}, Thomas Tanguy²

¹ Institut VEDECOM, 77 rue des Chantiers, 78000 Versailles, France

² Groupe PSA- Centre Technique de Vélizy A, Route de Gisy, 78140 Vélizy-Villacoublay, France

*Corresponding author: roch.elkhoury@vedecom.fr

Introduction

As battery electric vehicles have a significantly higher tank-to-wheel efficiency, the auxiliary on-board consumes as much of energy as what is needed to propel the vehicle. Electrically powered Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning systems (HVAC) used to bring the thermal comfort to the cabin occupants can reduce by twofold the autonomy of the vehicle under certain operating conditions. Car manufacturers are thus challenged to produce EVs that match the performance, comfort, and safety of their internal combustion engine counterparts in order to push EVs from a niche into a mass market.

Reducing the power consumption of the HVAC system could be achieved by the application of local thermal conditioning, instead of acting on the whole cabin via air distribution. In order to achieve this objective, a reliable, accurate and predictive thermal comfort model is required to spot uncomfortable zones and set up a strategy to bring the passengers back to comfort as fast as possible with the minimum energy consumption. The Zhang model [1] is a good candidate for such an application because transient local thermal sensation and comfort are model outputs.

A systematic comparison of widely used thermal sensation models, carried out by B. Koelblen et al. [2], pointed out the wide discrepancies between their predictions. An experimental investigation has been carried out to test the validity of the Zhang model in a controlled thermal environment that can be encountered in car cabins.

Methods

A thermal test bench that represents a B-segment car cabin was used for the experiments. The internal walls of the test cell are covered with 42 independent flat stainless steel heat exchangers reproducing the car cabin geometry. Their temperatures can be precisely controlled from 5 to 45°C using an independent water-glycol circulation circuit. An air handling unit provides control over the mass flow rate, temperature, and humidity of the air that is injected into the cabin. Several temperature probes monitor surface, air as well as interface contact temperatures throughout the tests. Other environmental parameters like the black globe temperature, air humidity, and airflow velocities are also measured around the subjects.

The ten human test subjects that underwent the thermal exposure were provided with identical thermally characterized clothes for the experiments. They were also fitted with wireless skin temperature and humidity sensors at 36 different location of their bodies. Each tester went through the following exposure:

1. 30 minutes of sedentary preconditioning at 25°C in a separate room
2. 30 minutes in the driver seat inside the test bench at 45°C (air and surface temperatures)
3. 60 minutes during which the air and surface temperatures transition to 25 °C

Throughout the tests, airflow and humidity from the air handling unit were fixed at 250m³/h and 50% respectively. All temperature sensors were calibrated using a standard Pt100 thermometer with an accuracy of 0.2°C. During the experiments, skin temperatures, heart rate, and the environmental conditions were continuously measured at an interval of 10 seconds. Tympanic temperatures, as well as thermal sensation and comfort votes, were collected at a five minutes interval, the Zhang nine-point scale was used for the votes.

Local skin and tympanic temperature measurements were averaged over the 10 testers and fed into a standalone implementation of the Zhang thermal sensation and comfort algorithm [1] as well as the Fiala DTS thermal comfort algorithm [3]. The code validation has been carried out by feeding into our solver skin and core temperatures calculated by a commercial FIALA-FE solver and comparing sensations and comforts

obtained by our solver to the Zhang and DTS model results calculated by the commercial solver. An excellent agreement was found. The results were then confronted to the average local sensation and comfort votes that were recovered during the experiments (see Figs 1 and 2 where the mean vote is in plain line and the standard deviation is represented by a solid stripping around the mean vote).

Results and Discussion

The global sensation and comfort indices are shown in the figures below. It is clear that at the beginning of the exposure, the Zhang model is not able to reproduce the trend of the experimental votes due to the large temperature step change. The model catches up with the experimental results after the 50th minute of exposure for sensation.

On the other hand, the dynamic thermal sensation model (DTS) produces a better fit of the experimental results, especially at the beginning of the exposure. This comparison shows that for such exposures, the Zhang thermal sensation and comfort models suffer from a lagging response preventing them from reacting with the appropriate amplitude to the transient situation.

Fig.1: Vote vs. Zhang vs DTS for global sensation

Fig.2: Vote vs. Zhang for global comfort

Conclusion

Thermal sensation and comfort predicted by the Zhang and DTS models were confronted to experimental votes in a controlled transient thermal environment that reproduces a car cabin. Skin and core temperature measurements of 10 human subjects were fed into the models. Discrepancies between the experimental votes and predictions of the Zhang model were found to be quite high compared to those of the DTS model that provided a good fit.

Although the DTS model better fits the experimental data for global thermal sensation, it has a considerable limitation as it provides neither local thermal sensation nor comfort. The Zhang model will thus have to be better tuned to gain in accuracy in order to be able to address the thermal comfort challenges inside car cabins. Additional experimentation work is in progress to include more human subjects and investigate more test cases (tests in a cold environment for instance).

References

- [1] H. Zhang, Human thermal sensation and comfort in transient and non-uniform thermal environments, Ph.D. Thesis, University of California, Berkeley, 2003.
- [2] B. Koelblen, A. Psikuta, A. Bogdan, S. Annaheim and R.M. Rossi, Thermal sensation models: a systematic comparison, *Indoor Air*, vol. 27, Issue 3, may 2007.
- [3] D. Fiala, Dynamic Simulation of Human Heat Transfer and Thermal Comfort, Ph.D. Thesis, De Montfort University, Leicester, 1998.